

Cultural Consensus in Mental Models of Collaborative Decision Making

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Cultural differences in collaborative decision making are increasingly recognized as essential areas of investigation (Earley & Gibson, 2002; Peterson, Miranda, Smith, & Haskell, 2003; Staples & Zhao, 2006). This research trend largely mirrors corporate and government trends toward increasing reliance on multinational and multicultural teams to handle all manner of tasks, such as a multinational marketing team responsible for developing products for multiple-country markets or a team of coalition planners developing options for coordinating humanitarian assistance in response to a natural disaster. As corporate and governmental organizations place greater reliance on multinational and multicultural teams, it is critical to identify potential friction points where cultural misunderstandings could occur that would impact team effectiveness. One source of friction is in the mental models that culturally diverse team members have of the collaborative decision process itself. The purpose of this paper is to use an analytical technique for cultural modeling, Cultural Consensus Theory (CCT), to explore cultural commonalities and differences in mental models of collaborative decision processes.

In a multinational decision making team, members may have culturally-distinct expectations about how the team will function. For example, some members may expect decisions to be made by the entire team, while other members may expect the decision to be made solely by the leader. Research on team mental models has tended to find that greater commonalities in mental representations are associated with improved team performance (e.g., Rentsch & Klimoski, 2001). A team whose members possess discrepant mental models concerning the nature of teamwork is likely to suffer from process loss. This study sought to identify cultural similarities and differences in expectations for how teams will function.

Business professionals ($n = 163$) from India, South Korea, Turkey, and the United States completed a web-based survey designed to elicit values related to team competencies, including decision making, adaptability, performance monitoring, back-up behaviors, and motivation. Participants read statements about teamwork, such as “When a team member is having trouble completing a task, it is the other team members’ responsibility to help with the task,” and rated whether the statement was an example of good teamwork on a 7-point Likert-type scale anchored at Strongly Disagree (1) and Strongly Agree (7).

Cultural Consensus Theory (CCT) was conducted to analyze the data. CCT allows one to determine whether the data fit a shared cultural model, and provides measures of individual fit to that cultural model (e.g. Ross & Medin, 2005). The ratio between the first and second eigenvalues of 6.07 indicates that a single consensus model holds across all countries. This result suggests that Americans, Indians, South Koreans, and Turks hold a shared cultural model of values for team processes and performance. In addition, participants had a mean cultural competency of .58, which indicates that participants agreed with the consensus answers 58% of the time, on average. Individual cultural competencies ranged from .20 to .87. The results of a one-way ANOVA show no differences in cultural competencies across countries, $F(3, 122) = 1.36, p = .26$.

Overall, the cultural model of teamwork values tends to be aligned with Western models of team processes and team performance. The following team-related values were generally shared across cultures:

- Replanning is necessary at times. Both the team leader and team members are responsible for indicating when replanning should occur.
- Team members should help when other team members need assistance in completing their tasks.
- It should be the role of both the leader and the team members to monitor performance and identify potential problems.
- Team members as well as the leader should be included in the decision-making process. Furthermore, the decision-making process should include open discussion and evaluation of ideas.
- Team members should be more concerned with the welfare of the team than with their own individual interests.

This study provided initial evidence that Western prescriptions of competent teamwork are valued across a diverse set of countries. While there are many similarities, cultural variations in team process values do exist (McHugh, Smith, & Sieck, 2007). Future research should explore the relationship between these shared team values and current team practices.

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